

LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IS EASY WITH INFORMATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES AND GAMES

Khasanov Bakhrom

Computer science teacher at Gulistan State University

e-mail: xbaxrom@gmail.com

Khasanova Shakhlo Asatullaevna

Gulistan State university academic lyceum, a teacher of English

e-mail: khasanovashakhlo88.20.06@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This article discusses the importance of new information technologies in learning English, including the convenience and advantages of Internet resources.

Keywords: Method, information technology, internet resources, English, education, foreign language.

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini o'rganishda yangi axborot texnologiyalarining ahamiyati, jumladan, Internet resurslarining qulayligi va afzalliklari muhokama qilinadi.

Kalit so'zlar: Metod, axborot texnologiyalari, internet resurslari, ingliz tili, ta'lim, chet tili.

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье обсуждается важность новых информационных технологий в изучении английского языка, в том числе удобство и преимущества интернет-ресурсов.

Ключевые слова: метод, информационные технологии, интернет-ресурсы, английский язык, образование, иностранный язык.

INTRODUCTION

Informatization of society creates new forms of educational activity. Today it is generally recognized that young people should be prepared for life in the modern information society and have the necessary skills to work with information.

One of the priority areas for the modernization of higher education is the active use of new information technologies (NIT). New information technologies, among

which the Internet firmly holds the leading position, are designed to provide a qualitatively new level of education in higher education. At the present stage, most Russian universities are connected to the global Internet and local information networks.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In the teaching of foreign languages, there is also a positive trend in the active use of new forms of organization of the educational process. Innovative teachers fruitfully apply NIT in the course of foreign language teaching. Educational Internet portals in foreign languages are being created, computer classes are being opened. In the classroom, video materials are used, electronic textbooks are used, virtual tours and video conferences are held. Foreign language teachers are increasingly using project methods with the involvement of computer technology⁶⁵.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The advantages of using the global Internet with the proper organization of classroom and extracurricular work of students are obvious:

- provides access to huge volumes of constantly updated authentic media texts;
- the possibility of real oral and written communication with native speakers is provided and the skills of a culture of interethnic communication are developed;
- solving a number of didactic tasks is facilitated (the vocabulary of students is expanding, writing skills are improving, etc.);
- the general outlook of students is expanding and a stable motivation for learning foreign languages is formed;
- a student-centered approach to learning is being implemented;
- independent cognitive activity of students is activated and the foundations of research work are laid.

Studying a computer science course in a secondary school largely contributes to computer proficiency already at an elementary user level. As practice shows, most students actively use Word, Excel, Web Design, Power Point, etc. programs in their educational activities⁶⁶.

Thus, all of the above facts indicate that Internet technologies can be considered as one of the most effective means of optimizing learning activities in English classes.

In recent years, many works have been written by domestic and foreign researchers, which present the obvious advantages of using NIT in the educational

⁶⁵ Novikova A.A. Media education in English classes. Taganrog, 2014.P.34.

⁶⁶ Fedorov A.V. Media education and media literacy. Taganrog, 2014. P.187.

process. For example, a number of useful recommendations on the safe and efficient use of the Internet are contained in the scientific works of E.S. Polat and M.Y. Bukharkina. The problems of the use of media technologies in the English language classes are devoted to the work of domestic researchers (A.A. Novikova, N.P.Ryzhikh, I.M. Khizhnyak, etc.).

At the same time, the analysis of the studied literature allows us to conclude that the problem of developing the methodological application of Internet resources has not yet been sufficiently studied for their implementation in the educational process.

Within the framework of this article, we do not pretend to a detailed analysis of all the problems that arise in the course of classroom and extracurricular work of students when using Internet resources. Therefore, it seems appropriate to us to give a brief overview of such problems and consider possible ways to solve them.

The main disadvantages of using the Internet system in the educational process include the following:

- information resources of the educational segment of the Internet are not regulated by law;
- no one is responsible for the accuracy and reliability of online information;
- many electronic textbooks are not properly reviewed;
- numerous computer viruses are regenerated;
- the Internet contains materials with elements of racism, xenophobia, aggression, etc.;
- Excessive and uncontrolled use of the Internet contributes to the development of Internet addiction⁶⁷.

At the same time, modern media are increasingly taking on educational functions. Statistical data show that students are the most active consumers of mass media information, in particular, the Internet, which becomes for them one of the main sources of information, a means of understanding the world around them.

This creates a very contradictory situation. On the one hand, students are quite fluent in modern media technologies. On the other hand, it is difficult for them to navigate in the flow of constantly updated avalanche-like information. Many are subject to manipulation by the mass media, as they have not yet developed enough criteria for critical evaluation of information transmitted through various media channels.

Therefore, young students should have the skills to work with information arrays presented both in traditional and electronic formats.

⁶⁷ Stepanova M. M. Formation of the competence of business communication in a foreign language in the magistracy of a non-linguistic university // Scientific and technical statements of St. Petersburg State Polytechnical University. Humanitarian and social sciences. - St. Petersburg, 2013. - No. 2. - P. 108-112.

CONCLUSION

So, the effective and rational use of new information technologies (with an appropriate level of media literacy / media competence of students) significantly expands the scope of the educational process, increases its practical orientation, and allows raising the process of teaching a foreign language to a higher level. Computer skills are being improved, the language level and motivation in learning a foreign language are increasing. As a result, conditions are created for the successful self-realization of students, which in the future will help them become competitive specialists in the labor market and meet the high requirements of the information society.

REFERENCES

1. Novikova A.A. Media education in English classes. Taganrog, 2014.P.34.
2. Fedorov A.V. Media education and media literacy. Taganrog, 2014. P.187.
3. Stepanova M. M. Formation of the competence of business communication in a foreign language in the magistracy of a non-linguistic university // Scientific and technical statements of St. Petersburg State Polytechnical University. Humanitarian and social sciences. - St. Petersburg, 2013. - No. 2. - P. 108-112.
4. Yakovleva L.V. The use of information technologies in the process of teaching a foreign language /L. V. Yakovleva, T. G. Sobakar, E. V. Chernyak. - M., 2016. - P. 82.
5. www.lib.ru